

Construction of the Palace of Westminster: requirements and scope changes 1840s and 1850s.

Firms

Lees of Lambeth

Foreman George Allen

worked with Barry on Birmingham Grammar School.

Left the Parliamentary contracts in 1846 because of disputes over Prices and costing.

Thomas lived in 19 Kensington gardens in a house designed by Barry and using surplus Parliamentary stone.

Thomas Grissell and Henry Peto

1839-1843

River front block (East Range) and Black Rod.

1840-1852

central Range and connections with Westminster Hall etc.

1845-1847

The new facades to Westminster Hall.

1852-1857

Public facing block (west front) facing Old Palace Yard.

John Jay contractors

Henry Hope windows

Hardman

Stained Glass

Pugin as one of their designers

HARDMAN ARCHIVES PROJECT 2008-2009

Volunteers helped to catalogue and store the archives of John Hardman & Co in their Birmingham base. The majority of those archives are now in the Birmingham Museum and Art Gallery and in the Library of Birmingham. John Hardman & Co was established in 1838 when AWN Pugin persuaded his friend, John Hardman Jr to extend his button-making factory into the manufacture of ecclesiastical metalwork for the new gothic-revival churches that were being built to Pugin's design. In 1845, the company expanded to include the design and manufacture of stained glass. The archives include drawings, designs, photographs of world wide commissions including the Palace of Westminster and cathedrals in USA and Australia. The volunteers have been working in conjunction with Michael Fisher FSA, the archivist for John Hardman.

Birmingham

Messenger and Sons

Ornamental Brass

chandeliers

candelabras

Gas fittings

Iron railings for staircases

for Brass Gates for Lords chamber

Ironmaster Henry Grissell

alongside his brother

Regent's canal Ironfounders and contractors

opened 1841

supplied 'portions' of the Westminster Cast Ironwork

HOL Windows

Ballantine and Allen

Stationary steam engines

Soho Foundry Preston

Joseph Clayton and Sons of Preston

The heating boilers

Construction Materials

Wrought Iron

Galvanised cast Iron

stone - clad brick walls in the tower

Thames Bank workshops

stone and wood carvers

Massive expense to train new carvers

Amended or changing requirements

1840s

Railway Mania

Big need for Committee Rooms

By 1835, Lords wanted more convenient accommodation

By 1835 Commons wanted more...

Library Rooms

Committee Rooms

Additional Division Lobby

By 1837, Commons wanted...

Even bigger Library

more Committee Rooms

1851

still required

Letter racks

coat Hooks

Inkwells

Umbrella Stands

Refreshment Rooms

Libraries

Lobbies

Tiling schemes

cast Iron Roof Tiles

Because of the Reid plan for heating and ventilation

and the danger of fire

Transfer to operations?

February

1853

Alfred Meeson becomes the building services engineer

Barry's assistant since 1842

His own practice was in Wakefield

Appointed by Barry to oversee the structural engineering detail

Meeson led the design of the fireproof ironwork

The floor and seating in both Houses is supported on cast iron columns and raking girders. The pitched roofs are constructed with cast iron plate-clad trusses screwed to the rafters.

Fireproof construction

flooring

Roof Tiles

Initial Requirements?

Commons

strangers Dining Room

Members Dining Room

kitchen

Wine cellars

Two Prison rooms

Clerks to be allotted office space

speaker to have own Residence

Library

Accommodation for librarian

Additional shelving space elsewhere

A debating chamber as wide as it was long

Accommodation for four fifths of MPS

connected to voting lobbies

Room for meeting strangers

30 committee Rooms

Small, medium, large

Lords

Similar to Commons

Robing Room for Monarch

Six committee Rooms

four waiting rooms

coffee Room

Dining Suite

Residence for Black Rod

Doorkeepers Dressing Room

Librarian apartment-5 rooms

Two large fireproof repositories-not less than 8 thousand square feet

Private Rooms

clerks

Lord Chancellor

Archbishop York

Archbishop Canterbury

Archbishop Dublin

Rooms for 24 Bishops

Additional rooms for supporting staff

chamber to hold 300 Peers

Large lobby for Commons to wait for audiences

Ceremonial Entrance

Key Concerns

Ventilation

based on experience of the old chambers

The building design and initial construction commenced without finalising air treatment and heating

Stonework

1838 Barry goes on a tour of quarries

1836 Barry commissions Pugin to work up interior sketches

to form basis for estimates

Priority

The 2 Chambers

Royal Gallery and staircase

Robing Room

other Principal floor rooms

1839

In June Barry Tenders out to 10 firms to build the 'Carcase' of the Building